

Guidelines for the Use of AI in Teaching and Examinations at the Department of Psychology

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Preamble

This document articulates a shared framework for addressing the opportunities and risks associated with the transformative impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on teaching and assessment at the Department of Psychology, LMU Munich. It has four parts:

- (1) Core Principles
- (2) Legal Framework: Academic Integrity in the Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence
- (3) "AI Basics" for Instructors and Students
- (4) Impulses for Teaching in Higher Education

We seek to foster a shared understanding and support professional exchange on the use of AI in teaching and assessments. Responsibility for the specific design of courses and assessments, as well as decisions regarding the use of AI, remains with individual instructors within the framework of current examination regulations; this upholds academic freedom in teaching as a central pillar of our university practice.

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20606212

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Part 1: Core Principles

1. Core Principles on AI in Teaching

The Department of Psychology at LMU Munich supports a reflective and responsible use of AI technologies. We consider the competent and appropriate use of AI as a key skill that students should acquire during their studies in order to prepare them effectively for careers both within and outside academia.

We recognize that the use of AI in teaching can open new possibilities, stimulate transfer of learning, and optimize the acquisition of knowledge and competencies.

We aim to leverage the opportunities offered by these technologies while minimizing risks, particularly regarding data protection, ethical standards, misconceptions about AI and the reliability of AI outputs, and scientific integrity. We seek to give our students the time and space to develop their own well-founded knowledge, shaped by our expertise and cultivated through our teaching. We are convinced that unrestricted use of AI technologies jeopardizes these processes and can impair knowledge acquisition as well as the development of critical thinking. At the same time, we are aware that a general prohibition would unnecessarily limit space for innovation, experimentation, and scientific advancement—also important goals of our higher-educational mission.

Instructors in the department commit to reviewing the recommendations for teaching and the technical foundations on AI contained in Parts 3 and 4 of these guidelines, to apply them in their teaching to the best of their ability, and commit to staying informed about ongoing developments.

These guidelines were finalized in June 2026 and reflect the technological and institutional conditions current at that time. Given the dynamic development of AI technologies, the guidelines are intended to be reviewed regularly and updated as needed.

2. Guiding Principles on Assessment

In accordance with the EU AI Act, the use of generative AI for grading assessments without human validation is not permitted at the Department of Psychology, LMU.

The use of AI in the Department of Psychology may only be expected for the successful completion of exams if the necessary competencies have been taught or ensured beforehand, and if data-protection-compliant and free access to AI systems is guaranteed for all students.

Instructors at the Department of Psychology seek to avoid an implicit elevation in performance expectations resulting from the growing availability of AI. At the same time, it may be appropriate to review and, where necessary, adapt assessment criteria in light of changing conditions. For example, the weighting of individual criteria may shift. In certain contexts (e.g., term papers), it may be appropriate to place less weight on aspects that are made easier by AI use and require less individual effort—such as linguistic accuracy in terms of spelling and grammar. Whether and to what extent such adjustments are made remains at the discretion of the instructor, guided by the relevant learning objectives, and will be communicated transparently to students at an early stage.

Part 2: Academic Integrity in the Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence

1. Purpose and Scope

This section articulates the department's shared understanding of academic integrity in the context of generative artificial intelligence (GenAI; e.g., large language models and similar systems) at the Department of Psychology, LMU Munich. It applies to all unproctored assessment formats (portfolios, term papers, assignments, presentations, and theses) across all degree programs offered by the department.

This policy is intended not only to uphold academic standards, but also to provide clarity and reassurance to students about responsible and acceptable academic practice.

2. Core Principle: Intellectual Authorship

Academic integrity is fundamentally a matter of intellectual authorship and responsibility. A lack of academic integrity occurs when plagiarism is present: plagiarism refers to the unmarked and unauthorized use of another person's work and the false claim of authorship.

Academic integrity is also compromised when any practice – technological or otherwise – replaces the author's own intellectual engagement.

Work submitted for academic credit must represent the student's own intellectual effort, understanding, and judgment.

Assessments are designed not merely to produce a correct or polished outcome, but to develop and assess students' thinking, including:

- reasoning and problem-solving,
- analytical and interpretive judgment,
- synthesis of ideas,
- methodological and conceptual decision-making.

3. Expectation of Intellectual Independence

Students are expected to:

- work independently on assigned tasks unless collaboration is explicitly authorized;
- invest a substantial amount of their own intellectual ability in completing coursework;
- submit work whose ideas, structure, reasoning, and conclusions they can explain, justify, and reconstruct independently.

4. Generative AI: Support vs. Substitution

We distinguish clearly between permissible supportive and impermissible substitutive uses of generative AI.

4.1 Permissible (Supportive) Uses

Unless explicitly excluded by the instructor because it would conflict with the learning objectives of an assignment, generative AI may be used to a limited extent, for example for:

- clarifying concepts or terminology in addition to—never as a replacement for—the primary scientific literature provided by instructors;
- reviewing one’s own understanding;
- reviewing self-written analysis code;
- generating ideas (without adopting AI-generated structure or arguments);
- revising self-written texts for language (e.g., style, grammar, and clarity).

In all cases, the student must retain full intellectual control and understanding of the submitted work.

4.2 Impermissible (Substitutive) Uses

The following uses are generally not permitted, unless explicitly made part of the assignment by the instructor:

- having generative AI complete assessments;
- generating and uncritically adopting arguments, analysis code, proofs, interpretations, or solutions that were not independently developed or at least critically revised and checked;
- allowing AI to determine the core logic or conclusions of an assignment.

In summary: If generative AI performs the core thinking the assignment is designed to develop or assess, its use constitutes a violation of academic integrity.

4.3 Guiding Test for Appropriate Use

As a general guideline, students and instructors may apply the following test:

Could the author reasonably explain, defend, and reconstruct the submitted work without reliance on a generative AI tool?

This test is intended to guide responsible learning and self-assessment, not to create unnecessary suspicion or anxiety. If the answer is no, the use of GenAI is not compatible with academic integrity.

5. Transparency and Accountability

Students remain fully responsible for all submitted work, regardless of any tools used in its preparation.

5.1 Good-Faith Learning Use

The department recognizes that students may use emerging tools in good faith while still learning how to apply them responsibly. When students act transparently, follow course-specific guidelines, and seek clarification when unsure, such use will not be considered misconduct.

6. Declaration of Independent Work /Declaration of Authorship

Students must include the following signed declaration (handwritten or digital) with their work:

I hereby declare that I have written this work independently. Any passages taken from other works, whether verbatim or in substance, have been clearly identified and appropriately referenced in every instance. This also applies to direct quotations from sources written in other languages that have been translated using AI tools. In such cases, I have cited both the original-language source and the AI tool used for

translation (e.g., “Author, Year, Page Number, translation of the original German-language source using DeepL”). Any drawings, maps, figures, or visual representations that have been reproduced from existing works or adapted for the purposes of this submission have been appropriately referenced.

AI-generated images have been clearly identified as such, and the tool used has been named.

Any AI-generated text or analysis code used in this work has been critically reviewed and, where necessary, revised by me.

I take full responsibility for the content of this work and confirm that I could reasonably explain, defend, and reconstruct it without relying on a generative AI tool.

7. Consequences of Impermissible Use

In the event of a suspected violation of academic integrity, formal proceedings to investigate academic misconduct will be initiated. The student concerned must be immediately informed by the examiner and given an opportunity to respond at an oral hearing (or, in exceptional cases, in writing). The purpose of the hearing is solely to clarify the facts relating to the suspected misconduct. This means it is only used to determine whether misconduct occurred (i.e., whether the concerned examination is graded as "failed" or not), not for further grading. If the concerned student does not utilize the opportunity for a hearing or to provide a statement, the decision must be made based on the evidence available. In principle, the university bears the burden of proof to provide evidence for the alleged act of deception. Therefore, the evidence, the procedure, and the outcome of any oral hearing must be thoroughly documented.

8. Instructional Autonomy

Individual instructors may specify more specific, more permissive, or more restrictive rules regarding GenAI use in their courses, provided these rules are consistent with the principle of academic integrity as set out in this document, and as long as they are in compliance with legal requirements. Course-specific guidelines take precedence where stated and communicated at the beginning of the course.

Part 3: "AI Basics" for Instructors and Students

1. Foundational Understanding of AI

Generative artificial intelligence refers to systems that can create new content, such as text, code, audio, or images, based on large datasets. Well-known applications include large language models that respond to user inputs ("prompts") and generate answers accordingly.

These systems are trained on very large amounts of text from the internet. In doing so, they learn statistical patterns in language, that is, which words and phrases frequently occur together. Based on this, the AI predicts the most probable continuation of text.

Generative AI, however, does not possess an understanding of meaning, truth, or context in the human sense. It generates responses based on statistical probabilities in the training data.

2. Key Limitations and Risks

Several limitations must be considered when using generative AI:

Error-Proneness: AI systems can generate incorrect information or invent sources ("hallucinations"). In the context of literature research, for example, AI applications may attribute topics to a paper that are not actually covered in it. For this reason, AI-generated claims should always be verified. If verification is not possible, the information should not be used.

Bias and Perspective Distortions: Responses may reproduce biases from training data or reinforce assumptions contained in the user's input. Examples: Frequently cited or salient events may be presented as more typical than they are. Example: The prompt "Prove that X is bad" leads to a one-sided, confirmatory response.

Lack of Transparency: The functioning of many AI systems (especially those from commercial providers) is only partially transparent, particularly regarding training data and decision-making processes.

Data Protection and Copyright: Entering sensitive content (e.g., personal data or unpublished work) may raise data protection and copyright issues.

Conversation Illusion: Interaction with AI in many common applications (e.g., ChatGPT) structurally resembles human conversation. However, many characteristics of human communication do NOT apply to AI:

- In humans, eloquent language is usually an indicator of solid knowledge – in AI, there is no reliable relationship between eloquence and content quality. AI systems can present content in a very convincing and fluent linguistic form. The linguistic quality of a response, however, says nothing about its factual accuracy or scientific validity.
- Human statements often contain (indirect) cues about the certainty of the statement – in AI, there are no such cues indicating whether statements are based on numerous or isolated data points, or are simply fabricated.
- Humans disagree and hold their own positions – AI tends toward confirmation and saying what feels good to the user, and often encourages further use by suggesting follow-up questions.

Responsibility Paradox: The design of AI suggests that one is having a conversation with a human. When it comes to responsibility, however, we expect users to be aware that they are dealing with a machine that can make errors, and to keep the limitations of AI outputs in mind. From a psychological perspective, this is a significant challenge.

Overtrust and Overgeneralization: Various biases in human information processing promote the development of overtrust – that is, excessive trust in AI beyond its actual capabilities. These include, for example, failure to verify AI results and general trust in AI after repeated positive experiences in individual cases (overgeneralization, positivist thinking), overestimation of one's own contribution in AI-assisted texts (self-serving bias), and increasingly uncritical use as one's own dependence on AI grows, in order to continue justifying that use (dissonance reduction).

Competent use of generative AI, therefore, always requires critical evaluation of results.

3. Responsibility of Users

Regardless of AI tool use, students and instructors bear responsibility for any content they use, share, or publish. This applies particularly to scientific statements, quotations, and citations.

AI-generated content should therefore never be adopted without verification. For academic work, independent research in the relevant literature remains essential.

4. Tools

The availability of AI tools is subject to dynamic developments. The focus is not on the variety of tools used, but on their reflective and responsible application. The following link provides a thematically structured, regularly updated collection of AI tools for academic reading and writing. Responsibility for the content remains with the author.

- Published under CC BY 4.0 and maintained by: Nils Van Quaquebeke https://docs.google.com/document/d/1mb4SWtqyi1iEGCn2uTnHkPHqW3UoQr8b0xv5_81a-4Y/edit?tab=t.0

5. Basics of Prompt Engineering

Because the quality of AI-generated responses depends heavily on how prompts are formulated, a basic understanding of prompt engineering is helpful for responsible and effective AI use. The following points provide guidance on which elements can help formulate clearer prompts and better contextualize results.

Elements of a Good Prompt

The quality of generative AI responses depends heavily on how the prompt is formulated. A clearly formulated prompt helps the AI deliver more relevant results. Typical components of a good prompt include:

- **Clear Task Description:** A precise description of what the AI should do (e.g., explain, summarize, list, present in tabular form).

- **Contextual Information:** Relevant background information on the topic, the purpose of the request, or the subject-specific framework (e.g., psychological approach, study context).
- **Target Audience or Perspective:** Indication of who the response is intended for (e.g., bachelor's students, academic audience).
- **Desired Response Format:** Guidance on the structure of the output (e.g., bullet points, short paragraph, table, comparison).
- **Scope and Focus:** Indications of how detailed the response should be and which aspects should be particularly emphasized.

6. Learning Opportunities for Acquiring AI Competence

The following links provide thematically structured, regularly updated collections of freely available learning resources on AI. Responsibility for the content remains with the respective authors.

In light of current legal frameworks (cf. Art. 4 EU AI Act), which place a particular responsibility on educational institutions to foster relevant competencies when using AI, these offerings can provide helpful orientation and support.

- Published and maintained by: Stifterverband für Künstliche Intelligenz (content in German and English): <https://ki-campus.org/>
- Published and maintained by the appliedAI Institute for Europe, a non-profit organization based in Heilbronn and Munich (registration required; content in German and English): <https://lms.appliedai-institute.de/>
- Published and maintained by Elements of AI, a Finnish consultancy MinnaLearn and the University of Helsinki (content in German and English): <https://www.elementsofai.de/>

Part 4: Impulses for Teaching in Higher Education

The development and widespread availability of artificial intelligence is fundamentally changing teaching, learning, and assessment at universities. The aim of these guidelines is not to prevent or prohibit these developments, but to continue ensuring high-quality scientific education for students. While not all assessment formats can be fully protected against inappropriate AI use, teaching and learning processes can be designed to foster core competencies, achieve learning objectives, and sustainably strengthen academic work.

Instructors at the Department of Psychology commit to reviewing the following **checklist** at the beginning of each course. The purpose of the checklist is not to restrict academic freedom, but to encourage instructors to address the topic of 'artificial intelligence' and communicate to their students what applies and is expected for the respective course and thesis. The checklist should be applied consistently across courses that share common assessment formats, e.g., for the empirical research practicum.

1. Checklist for Instructors

<u>1. Learning Objectives and Use of AI</u>	
<input type="checkbox"/>	I have clearly defined the learning objectives and explained how AI can be used to achieve them in alignment with academic integrity.
<input type="checkbox"/>	I have discussed my learning objectives and explained at which points the use of artificial intelligence can be meaningful or may be used in a supportive role to achieve them.
<input type="checkbox"/>	I have considered how I will assess the achievement of the learning objectives and how students can demonstrate this using AI tools while maintaining their academic integrity. In this context, I have explained the criteria by which I identify a suspected violation of the appropriate use of AI applications and have informed the students that the consequences include the initiation of an academic integrity investigation.
<u>2. Communication of the AI Guidelines</u>	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sections 1 to 3 of these AI guidelines are uploaded to my Moodle course, and I have informed students of their availability.
<u>3. Fostering AI Competencies</u>	
<input type="checkbox"/>	I take advantage of relevant learning opportunities to support the competent use of artificial intelligence and continuously develop my own competencies in this area.
<input type="checkbox"/>	I inform my students about suitable learning opportunities on the use of artificial intelligence. I make it transparent when the competencies taught there form an important foundation for successful participation in my course.
<input type="checkbox"/>	I support my students in acquiring basic competencies in the reflective and responsible use of artificial intelligence – also in light of current European developments (e.g., Art. 4 EU AI Act).

2. Pedagogical Recommendations for the Use of Artificial Intelligence in Teaching and Assessment

1. Aligning Assessment Formats Based with Learning Objectives

Proctored assessments (i.e., in-person exams) are particularly appropriate when the learning objectives require an individual, independent performance without external assistance. These include, above all, foundational knowledge, basic methodological skills, and core subject-specific competencies that are prerequisites for advanced learning.¹

Unproctored assessment formats (e.g., term papers, portfolios, project work) are better suited for assessing complex, reflective, and application-oriented competencies. In these formats, complete control or regulation of AI use is not possible and should therefore be considered when designing task and assessment criteria.

¹ In the context of proctored in-person exams, attention should be drawn to technological innovations for cheating, such as nearly invisible earbuds or so-called spy pens with wireless online connections.

2. Integrating Practice Time and Independent Production Phases into Teaching

Courses should intentionally include practice time and independent production phases. In these phases, students build the competencies that will later be assessed. They also increase transparency regarding which performances are expected from students individually and will be assumed in the further course of study.

3. Considering Process-Oriented Working Methods

In addition to evaluating the final product, the work process can also be integrated into teaching and assessment. This can be done, for example, through interim submissions, brief reflections, or explanations of methodological decisions (example questions: Why did you choose this method? Which alternatives did you discard? Where did difficulties arise and how were they resolved?). Such process-oriented elements give instructors better insight into students' learning and reflection processes. This makes individual learning processes more transparent, particularly to students themselves, promotes academic reflection, and practices supportive rather than substitutive uses of AI.

4. Implementing AI Usage Limitations Where Justified by Specific Competency Goals and Technically Verifiable

Restrictions on AI use are appropriate and justified when they are pedagogically grounded and technically and organizationally feasible to implement. This includes, in particular, that requirements and restrictions are clearly communicated to students and that compliance can be verified, for example through suitable task formats, assessment forms, or accompanying reflection and documentation requirements. The goal is to promote a transparent, competency-oriented, and responsible use of AI tools, rather than restricting it categorically.